

PEDAGOGICAL INTERACTION IN EDUCATION AND EDUCATION

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Abstract. *The most important process in the educational system is pedagogical interaction in education and upbringing. Its importance, its role in educational processes, its position in the relationship between a teacher and a pupil or student, including opinions and reasonable information about the aspects that should be recognized separately, are reflected in the content of the article. Also, the history of pedagogical interaction, the stages of development in pedagogical processes were also given importance in the formation of the article.*

Keywords: *education, upbringing, pedagogical interaction, pedagogical process, educational system, pedagogy, teacher, pupil or student, typologies of pedagogical interaction.*

The study of interactions in various spheres of life is one of the trends of the modern scientific world and thinking today. This is primarily due to the changes in the social and cultural spheres associated with the processes of democratization of consciousness, and the orientation of science to the study of problems related to the individual. It should be noted that in this case, a clear contradiction between "interaction" (considered as a concept and a category of pedagogic science) and the quality of its scientific development is identified, which leads to a reduction in the understanding of the phenomenon.

In the arsenal of pedagogic science, there are terms "pedagogical interaction" and "pedagogical influence". How new are these phenomena?

Does it have a unique learning history?

Does it belong to the main categories of pedagogy or is it just nominated?

Is it concentrated in the field of teacher-student relations, or does it cover an important range of social, psychological, pedagogical problems?

How are the content and forms of pedagogical interaction revealed in the educational process?

Will the nature of these interactions change in the information age? And so on.

It is clear from these questions that pedagogy as a science has collected a large amount of research in the field of interaction of education. However, the directions and diagnostic tools aimed at studying them are changing in accordance with the modernization processes in the educational system. Therefore, at each stage of the development of the educational system, there is a need for research that can provide a scientific-theoretical analysis and practice-oriented evaluation of the processes and events that make up pedagogical (educational) interactions.

If you look at the history of pedagogy and its development, you can see that interaction in pedagogy in the 50s and 60s of the 20th century was related to the theory of learning. For example, in didactics, this interaction was manifested in the following connections: principles of teaching (the connection between theory and practice, the principle of harmonizing individual and collective approaches in the organization of teaching, etc.), teaching methods (where the success of using methods is determined by their harmony idea is emphasized) and place.

Later, by the 70s of the last century, it was emphasized in the field of education to understand the pedagogical interaction. It is this issue that Russian scientists V.A. Karakovsky, H.J. Liimets, L.I. Novikova, V.D. Semenov, A.N. Tubelsky, N.E. Shchurkova's scientific research and some of his works are raised. It is their concepts such as "educational interaction" and "educational systems" that are put in the center of this problem.

Pedagogical interaction itself as a term was nominated in the textbook "Pedagogy" edited by Y.K. Babansky in 1988, where teachers were the first to use the term pedagogical interaction in the process of school communication. and it was emphasized that mutual activity and cooperation of students will be reflected.

It should be noted that today the definition of pedagogical interaction is no longer considered as a term, but as a category, because this category reflects the most important and natural connections and relations of reality and knowledge. This, of course, also applies to pedagogical interaction, which is the sole purpose and mechanism of all processes that take place in the educational space.

The end of the 20th century should be noted as another stage in the history of interaction pedagogy. The fact that this period is connected with the formation of social pedagogy as an independent direction of science and practice is not an unknown issue for all representatives of the field of pedagogy. It is known that the founders of the direction, such as L.V. Mardakhayev, A.V. Mudrik, directly or indirectly referred to the mutual relations of different individuals as a tool for organizing the appropriate pedagogical process. And it should be said that for many practicing teachers, the recommendations and examples described in the manual created by them served as an important guide in the construction of their pedagogical activities.

In the next decade, that is, from the end of the eighties of the last century, pedagogical interaction was included in the content of dictionaries, encyclopedias and textbooks on pedagogy and psychology. It should be emphasized that interaction becomes the basis that clearly reveals many concepts of the pedagogical process. Previously, it was the concept of exposure to familiar phenomena and concepts, but now interaction is emphasized as the basis of pedagogical processes. The subject-subject nature of the relations between the participants of the educational process was a characteristic of the pedagogical studies of that time. This feature is also reflected in the scientific research of scientists E.N. Gusinsky and L.D. Stolyarenko.

The growing interest in pedagogical interaction as a phenomenon and leading category of pedagogical science naturally created the need for a certain systematization of the collected data, knowledge and experience. This, in turn, led to the emergence of typologies, classifications, etc., of various forms and content. The following are examples of currently known typologies of pedagogical interactions:

typology based on the ratio of adult and child participation in joint activities. It represents guardianship, coaching, partnership, cooperation, team;

typology describing the level of participation of the teacher in the organization of the child's life. In this typology, it can be said that the teacher protects the student, helps him on various topics, supports the student in various processes and accompanies the student in any situation and event;

a typology that determines the position of the teacher based on the harmony of his attitude to the activity and his attitude to the students;

typology that reveals similarities and differences in opinions and assessments of subjects: agreed, neutral, inconsistent.

When talking about typologies of pedagogical interactions, it should be noted that classifications describing interpersonal interactions in one way or another have certain limitations. For example, age, field of activity, specific features of the scientific approach, etc. Therefore, the approach to pedagogical interactions, which allows combining several, can be used in practical processes. Thus, according to the direction and results of the process of pedagogical interaction within the framework of typology, it is a very important aspect to study the positions of the teacher, to determine the basis of similarities and differences in the evaluation of the subjects of the educational environment.

When expressing an opinion about pedagogical interaction or talking about its role and importance in practical processes, one should not forget another important aspect, which is that pedagogical interaction is an independent phenomenon, and it is necessary to become a scientific category. It has its own history. It turned from one-time notes to mastering conceptual features, and then to a leading scientific pedagogical category. Peculiarities of pedagogical interaction include: universality and relativity, integrity and self-sufficiency, causality, selectivity.

Today, pedagogical interaction is a link between educational subjects and objects, determined by the cognitive situation, associated with socio-psychological processes, leading to their quantitative and/or qualitative change. It can also be interpreted as an integrative basis of education. The system, which defines both the structure and content of this system, ensures the connection of education with other social institutions, and also determines the direction and methods of communication of subjects engaged in educational activities.

We know that any process is a continuous transition from one state to another. In the pedagogical process, it is the result of pedagogical interaction. Therefore, pedagogical interaction is recognized as an important feature of the pedagogical process. Unlike any other interaction, it is a long-term or temporary relationship between a teacher and a learner, the result of which is a mutual change in their behavior, activities, and attitudes. are changes.

Pedagogical interaction is a pedagogical effect manifested in the direct or indirect influence on the teacher and himself, that is, on self-education. Mystery, its active perception and assimilation by the student, as well as his own activity. Such an understanding of pedagogical interaction allows to identify the two most important components in the structure of both the pedagogical process and the pedagogical system - teachers and students, who are their most active elements.

We know very well that the pedagogical process is carried out in specially organized conditions, primarily related to the content and technology of pedagogical interaction. Thus, two more components of the pedagogical process and system are distinguished: educational content and educational tools (material, technical and pedagogical forms, methods). The interaction of the components of the system, such as the teacher and students, the content of education and its tools creates a real pedagogical process as a dynamic system. They are sufficient and necessary for the emergence of any pedagogical system.

Research in the field of pedagogical interaction will always remain relevant as a scientific and practical direction. The diversity and problematic nature of the study of this phenomenon is primarily due to its scope, which covers both the interpersonal relationships of the participants of educational activities and the general processes that occur in local and global educational systems.

In addition, it should not be overlooked that it has an interdisciplinary nature and is related to the development of the possibilities of the new information and communication environment. In addition, it is important to study the issue of pedagogical interaction at the level of pedagogical research methodology and emphasize that it corresponds to the current level of development of educational theory and practice.

It would not be wrong to recognize the pedagogical interaction as a system of interrelated actions of the teacher and the learner in all areas of the educational process, as a process of their cooperation. . In this case, the teacher's activity is focused on finding ways to improve the position of each student in his personal life. In particular, it is manifested in self-development, acquisition of knowledge and formation of professional skills. The general logic of pedagogical cooperation is determined by the structure of effective pedagogical activity and includes the following stages: motivational, research, prognostic, initiative-corrective, design, organizational, reflective-evaluation. This structure makes it possible to implement subject-subject relations with the leader of the teacher in the "teacher-student (pupil)" formula.

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